

Magnetic reversibility accompanied by thermal hysteresis in magnetocaloric materials: A lock-in thermography study

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ABSTRACT

Lock-in infrared thermography (LIT) was used to obtain the reversible adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{ad}^{rev}) from an oscillating magnetic field up to a maximum of 1.5 T. Several paradigmatic magnetocaloric materials exhibiting diverse thermomagnetic phase transitions were studied: (1) Gd, undergoing a second-order transition; (2) $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ undergoing a magneto-elastic first-order transition; and (3) $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ and (4) $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ Heusler alloys, both undergoing magneto-structural first-order transition with varying degrees of overlap with the second-order transition of austenite and associated hysteresis. LIT increases ΔT_{ad}^{rev} resolution by two orders of magnitude compared to traditional thermography. This advanced capability facilitates the detection of features in the responses that would otherwise be challenging to identify. Furthermore, the phase Φ with respect to the excitation serves as an indicator of the phase transition dynamics. Importantly, while the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} measurements remain reversible against field oscillations, first-order thermomagnetic phase transitions driven by non-saturating fields show different behaviors for heating and cooling curves, manifesting thermal hysteresis and the irreversibility of the transition under those conditions. This highlights the significance of direct characterization methods of the magnetocaloric response over indirect approaches and its usefulness for the design of materials for efficient refrigeration devices.

1. Introduction

According to the International Energy Agency [1], due to the global warming aggravated by the increasing population and higher living standards in warm countries, such as India, Indonesia and China, energy consumption for space cooling is expected to triple by 2050. Most temperature control systems are based on vapor compression/expansion. However, this technology presents two important disadvantages: low energy efficiency and the use of refrigerants with a high global warming potential, such as hydrochlorofluorocarbons and hydrofluorocarbons [2,3], whose use has to be dramatically reduced by 2045 according to the ratified Kigali Amendment to the Montreal Protocol [4]. In the last few decades, magnetic refrigeration (MR) technology has been proven as a promising alternative to traditional cooling methods. Its energy-efficient operating cycle helps reduce operation costs and is environmental-friendly as it uses solid-state refrigerants that do not deplete the ozone layer. In addition, it avoids the risks associated with

toxicity or flammability. This technology takes advantage of the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) [5–7], the entropy/temperature change that occurs in a magnetic material when isothermally/adiabatically subjected to a varying magnetic field. Even though various MR prototypes have emerged [8–15], the commercial implementation of MR into the consumer market is still delayed due to several scientific and technological bottlenecks. Most efforts are currently focused on improving materials performance by finding the right balance between economically viable constituents and their functional effectiveness [16–19]. In this context, the order of the thermomagnetic phase transition plays a crucial role in determining their magnetocaloric properties. First-order thermomagnetic phase transitions (FOPT) tend to produce more promising results compared to second-order magnetic phase transitions (SOPT), which show moderate responses. However, the challenges associated with irreversibility and hysteresis in FOPT hinder their practical applicability up to the moment.

In addition to the mainstream application of MCE for temperature

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control near room temperature, there are ongoing efforts to apply it in other temperature ranges, such as the liquefaction of hydrogen. The goal of these efforts is to make this new energy vector more economically viable [20].

Gd is considered the paradigmatic SOPT magnetocaloric material, with its Curie temperature occurring at room temperature. However, it shows a moderate MCE response in low magnetic fields. Following the discovery of the so-called giant magnetocaloric effect in $\text{Gd}_5\text{Si}_2\text{Ge}_2$ by V. Pecharsky *et al.* [21], which is associated with a first-order magneto-structural transition, much of the research nowadays focuses on optimizing the MCE response in refrigerant materials that undergo this type of transition. Other FOPT materials showing notable MCE responses include the $\text{La}(\text{Fe},\text{Si})_{13}$ alloys, which undergo magneto-elastic transition [22–26]. In an effort to transit away from the use of rare-earth elements, research has increasingly focused on alternative material families, such as Mn-Fe-P-As alloys [27–30] and Mn-Fe-Si-based alloys [31–34] (which avoid the use of As from the previous alloys). Additionally, Ni-Mn-based Heusler alloys, including Ni-Mn-X (where X = Ga, In or Sn) [35–37] have been explored. Furthermore, recent studies have reported enhanced mechanical performance with improved MCE responses in the novel all-*d*-metal Ni(Co)Mn-Ti Heusler alloys, which exhibit a martensitic transformation near room temperature [38–42].

These magnetocaloric materials are frequently characterized by calculating the isothermal entropy change (ΔS_{iso}) from other experimentally measured magnitudes, either magnetization or heat capacity [43]. However, this indirect determination is only an estimate of the applicability of the materials. Moreover, MCE materials are used in actual MR devices under dynamic conditions, which involve the continuous application and removal of an external excitation field. Consequently, it is essential to investigate the cyclability of MCE materials, along with the influence of thermal hysteresis and the heat transfer dynamics in the regenerators, to facilitate their implementation in practical applications. To achieve this objective, it is necessary to establish a direct characterization methodology that will effectively assess the $\Delta T_{\text{ad}}^{\text{rev}}$. Temperature measurements using contact sensors, such as thermocouples [44], are generally better suited for large samples since the thermal mass of the sample needs to exceed that of the thermocouple. However, when investigating new materials, the sample size is often minimized. In contrast, the optical beam deflection technique offers non-contact measurements, yet its implementation can be challenging [45], particularly when dealing with the inverse MCE. More recently, infrared thermography (IRT) [46–51] has been gaining attention. Being a non-contact measurement method, it allows for the simultaneous characterization of multiple small samples, potentially making it a high-throughput technique [52].

In conventional IRT, the $\Delta T_{\text{ad}}^{\text{rev}}$ of the sample at a certain temperature is determined by the difference between its temperature before and after subjecting it to a pulsed or oscillating magnetic field. The sign of this temperature difference reveals whether the response is direct or inverse. However, conventional IRT using moderately priced infrared cameras has a noticeable limitation: the noise level can be in the order of 140 mK, which affects the type of materials that can be effectively studied as well as the intensity of the magnetic field required. While cameras with higher thermal resolutions can enhance performance, they come with significantly increased costs, thereby making them a major investment in infrastructure. This financial barrier restricts broader adoption of the technique and hampers the ability to identify and detect fine details in the responses during phase transitions.

Addressing the above-mentioned challenges, we utilized lock-in infrared thermography (LIT) [53–55] with a significantly enhanced temperature resolution and characterized the reversible magnetocaloric responses of various key materials exhibiting different types of thermomagnetic phase transitions: FOPT ($\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$), SOPT (Gd) and a combination of both with varying degrees of phase transition overlaps ($\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ and the all-*d*-metal $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ Heusler alloys). Our results show that while these materials exhibit

reversible behavior upon the application and removal of the magnetic field, FOPT materials display hysteretic behavior in temperature. This contrasts with the usual held assumption inferred from the overlapping heating and cooling ΔS_{iso} curves [56], unless the AC field is sufficiently large to fully saturate the transition.

2. Materials and methods

The Gd sample, sourced commercially with 99.9 % purity, measures 5x7x0.5 mm. The all-*d*-metal $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ Heusler sample, previously produced by induction melting [57], measures 4x6x2.5 mm. The $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ sample, previously developed by arc melting [58], was shaped into a near right triangle, with sides measuring 4 and 4.5 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm. Additionally, a $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ (Calorivac-H) granule, approximately 1x2x0.2 mm in size, was kindly provided by Vacuumschmelze GmbH & Co. The Calorivac-H sample was produced using powder metallurgy as previously described in [59–61].

Isothermal entropy change was indirectly determined from magnetization measurements, performed in a LakeShore 8607 vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM), through a discrete approximation to the following equation:

$$\Delta S_{\text{iso}} = \mu_0 \int_{H_1}^{H_2} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_{p,H} dH \quad (1)$$

where μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of free space, H_1 and H_2 the start and final values of the magnetic field, M is magnetization and T temperature. For first-order thermomagnetic transitions, a discontinuous measurement protocol has been employed to avoid spurious peaks [43].

The LIT, also known as AC thermography or phase sensitive thermography [53], is a measurement technique and post-processing method for enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio. This method is particularly effective in detecting small increases in temperature, especially when the noise-equivalent temperature (NETD) plays a critical role and the response signal may be obscured by noise. The mode of operation is based on the application of a periodic excitation signal, which serves as a reference, while the response is simultaneously being measured. In the case of studying the MCE, the excitation signal is an alternating magnetic field, and the response corresponds to the temperature of the material. It is important that both the excitation and the response signals are with constant frequencies. Although the frequency of the response does not need to coincide with that of the excitation wave, it must be a multiple of it. Typically, for caloric effects, the response coincides with the first harmonic [54], provided that the field oscillates between 0 and its maximum value.

A custom-made LIT device has been developed to characterize the variation of $\Delta T_{\text{ad}}^{\text{rev}}$ as a function of temperature and magnetic field, as schematically presented in Fig. 1. Magnetic fields are generated by an electromagnet connected to a Danfysik SYSTEM 7000 current source, which regulates its output amplitude based on a voltage input driven by a BK Precision 4063 function waveform generator. The sample is mounted on a polytetrafluoroethylene tube using a high thermal conductivity GE varnish. A fluid, whose temperature is controlled by a Julabo CORIO™ CD-1000F thermostat, passes through the above-mentioned tube and sets the base temperature for the sample. The temperature changes of the sample were recorded using an Optris PI 640 infrared camera equipped with a 33° lens and 125 Hz frame rate. Additionally, the magnetic field is measured using a LakeShore 450 gaussmeter, with its analog output linked to the industrial process interface of the camera for straightforward synchronization. Samples were coated with a high IR emissivity, high conductivity and low-temperature paint (LabIR®). Synchronization of the devices, measurement protocols and data post-processing were all developed using MATLAB®.

We have to keep in mind that infrared radiation emission strongly decreases with decreasing temperature and that the emission peak shifts

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the device for the direct characterization of MCE materials through IRT: (1) Electromagnet, (2) Current source, (3) Waveform generator, (4) Gaussmeter, (5) Infrared camera, (6) Industrial process interface, (7) Thermostat, (8) Polytetrafluoroethylene tube, (9) Sample, (10) Computer.

to the far infrared range when temperature is significantly smaller than room temperature. Therefore, the proposed detection method is limited to temperatures above 255 K.

The excitation signal used in the LIT device serves as the reference for the procedure and corresponds to a sinusoidal magnetic field oscillating between 0 and a maximum field H_{max} , which can be represented as:

$$H = \frac{H_{max}}{2} \cdot \sin(\omega_{ref}t + \theta_{ref}) + \frac{H_{max}}{2} \quad (2)$$

where ω_{ref} is the frequency and θ_{ref} is the phase. This phase will be considered as the reference for any subsequent measurement and our focus will solely be on the differences relative to it. Thus, the application of this wave generates a response in the sample associated with the caloric effect, making it change temperature with respect to its original temperature (T_{offset}), expressed as:

$$T_{sample} = A \cdot \sin(\omega_{ref}t + \theta_{sig}) + T_{offset} \quad (3)$$

where we already assumed that the response frequency coincides with the driving frequency due to the oscillation of the magnetic field between 0 and H_{max} . A corresponds to the amplitude and θ_{sig} is the phase of the response signal. From here, the $|\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}|$ due to the caloric effect is related to the amplitude A as

$$|\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}| = 2A \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, the phase shift from the driving field is extracted as

$$\Phi = \theta_{sig} - \theta_{ref} \quad (5)$$

All these magnitudes are represented in Fig. 2.

To perform lock-in analysis [62] from the raw data, sinusoids with the same frequency of the driving field, one with the same phase and another shifted in 90° , are used as references. The experimentally obtained temperature oscillations are then multiplied by these reference signals and the DC parts of these transformed signals correspond to the in-phase and out of phase components of the response of the material. The total response of the material is calculated as the square root of the sum of the squares of the two components.

It is worth noting that the lock in analysis provides the amplitude of the oscillation. Therefore, to obtain the sign of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} , we need to take into account the phase shift Φ . The sign of $\cos(\Phi)$ indicates the direct/inverse (positive/negative, respectively) character of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} :

Fig. 2. Time dependence of the sinusoidal driving field (grey) and the measured response (blue) of a hypothetical sample with direct magnetocaloric effect in which there is a phase shift between excitation and response. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$$\Delta T_{ad}^{rev} = |\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}| \cdot \frac{|\cos(\Phi)|}{\cos(\Phi)} \quad (6)$$

The procedure described above is repeated for each pixel of the thermographic image, allowing us to obtain maps of the magnetocaloric response for each sample, or to the average response of specific areas of the sample, to obtain curves of their response as a function of temperature.

An additional consideration when analyzing magnetocaloric materials is that, for SOPT materials, the adiabatic temperature change can be expressed as a power law of the field, with an exponent related to the critical exponents of the material [63]:

$$\Delta T_{ad}^{rev} = H^{1/\Delta} f(t/H^{1/\Delta}) \quad (7)$$

where f is a scaling function, t is $T - T_c$, and Δ is the gap critical exponent. For the mean field case, the critical exponent α equals zero ($\alpha = 0$) and the field dependence of ΔS_{iso} and ΔT_{ad}^{rev} coincide [64]. This non-linearity in field dependence implies that the adiabatic temperature change in response to a sinusoidal excitation does not strictly correspond to the principal harmonic but there are higher harmonics involved. However, this is not a significant limitation. In the case of a mean field model, the coefficient of the second harmonic is one order of magnitude smaller than that of the principal harmonic. This transforms into an error margin for the mean field model of $\sim 5\%$ if the analysis is restricted to the main harmonic response. For low field oscillations, this error margin would be within the experimental noise. The phase is not affected by the higher order terms. As experimental confirmation, Gd data have been analyzed up to a field of 1.5 T. While the first harmonic has an amplitude of 1.70 K, the second has an amplitude of 0.03 K, confirming the theoretical predictions. For $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$, amplitudes of the first and second harmonics correspond to 2.03 and 0.09 K, respectively. This justifies disregarding the higher order contributions for the experimental field range used in this work.

In this work, temperature variations are characterized with LIT under the application of a sinusoidal magnetic field oscillating from 0 to $\mu_0 H_{max}$, where $\mu_0 H_{max}$ is 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.25 and 1.5 T, all at a frequency of 0.5 Hz, which is suitable for quasi-adiabatic conditions. All the analysis has been restricted to the first harmonic response. A temperature ramp rate of 0.08 K min^{-1} is chosen to control the base temperature of the sample.

3. Results and discussion

The characterization of the pure Gd sample, a paradigmatic example of a SOPT, is depicted in Fig. 3 a. The top panel displays the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} versus temperature, showing a maximum at the Curie temperature. This peak tends to slightly shift to higher temperatures as the magnetic field increases. This slight shift is influenced by the critical exponents of the SOPT [65]. The lower panel shows the Φ of the response, expressed in degrees, with respect to the application of the reference field waveform. This value remains relatively constant across the temperature and is near the zero-degree value, indicating that the increasing field induces a positive temperature change in the material under quasi-adiabatic conditions. This demonstrates the direct MCE behavior of Gd. In fact, the consistent deviation of this phase lag from zero is attributed to intrinsic phase lag inherent in the instrumentation and processing software; typically, this would be customarily nulled as a reference. The obtained ΔT_{ad}^{rev} values are rather similar to those reported in the literature [54,66–69].

The reversible temperature change characterization of $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ is depicted in Fig. 3 b. This alloy undergoes a first-order ferromagnetic to paramagnetic magneto-elastic transition with low thermal hysteresis (2.2 K). Its ΔT_{ad}^{rev} shows a sharp and narrow peak that broadens as temperature increases in response to an increasing magnetic field (top panel). The direct character of the magnetocaloric behavior is maintained, as seen in the Φ diagram (lower panel). However, there is a noticeable deviation from a constant value at around the transition temperature, where the phase lag shows a maximum. This difference in the behavior of Φ for first- and second-order phase transitions will be discussed further below.

The results obtained from the characterization of the reversible temperature response of the $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ Heusler alloy are presented in Fig. 3 c. This alloy undergoes a martensitic transition from a low magnetization martensite to a high magnetization austenite around room temperature, accompanied by a hysteresis of 23.4 K. At approximately 300 K, a negative ΔT_{ad}^{rev} peak can be observed, which is due to the magnetic-induced FOPT. Here, the inverse magnetocaloric behavior can be evidenced by the abrupt change in the phase lag, achieving approximately 180°. This indicates that the temperature of the material decreases upon the application of an increasing magnetic field. As the base temperature increases, Φ sharply decreases once more towards a baseline value close to 0°, signifying that the FOPT regime has been left behind. Consequently, the remaining ΔT_{ad}^{rev} response is primarily associated with the Curie transition of the austenite phase. Therefore, the material demonstrates a significant overlap between the first-order magneto-structural transition and the SOPT. This results in an abrupt change from the inverse character of the response at lower temperatures to the direct MCE at higher temperatures, consistent with the behavior observed by indirect measurements [58]. The application of larger fields serves to stabilize the magnetic austenite phase; thus, the negative peak of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} and the corresponding peak observed for Φ , subsequently shift and broaden towards lower temperatures with increasing field. Moreover, the imposition of a larger magnetic field increases the temperature response associated with the SOPT, causing its peak to shift towards higher temperatures with increasing field. This behavior aligns with observations reported for a similar alloy composition ($\text{Ni}_{46.3}\text{Mn}_{36.6}\text{Si}_{1.4}\text{In}_{15.7}$) [55], which was characterized using a significantly more expensive camera.

To put into proper context the advantages of using LIT in comparison to conventional thermography, the same experimental raw data of $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ for a (small) maximum field of 0.2 T was processed as conventional thermography data and compared with the LIT results (Fig. 4). It is evident that the conventional thermography data (blue squares) exhibit a noise level on the order of 0.140 K, which aligns with the NETD of the camera. A simple approach to decrease noise could be averaging the data points for each temperature, as shown by green

triangles in the figure. While this approach certainly reduces noise, it introduces uncertainty in accurately determining the inverse magnetocaloric peak for this small applied field. In contrast, the implementation of LIT (orange spheres) results in an enhancement of temperature resolution exceeding one order of magnitude compared to classical thermography. This advancement effectively addresses the main limitation associated with conventional low-cost infrared hardware, thereby enabling reliable determination of the onset of the inverse magnetocaloric effect peak.

The last studied composition is an all-*d*-metal $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ Heusler. Similar to the previous case, this material exhibits a certain degree of overlap between the martensitic and Curie transitions (Fig. 3 d); however, this overlap is considerably less pronounced compared to the previously studied alloy. As with the earlier case, the high-temperature phase is stabilized by field, resulting in the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} peak shifting and broadening towards lower temperatures with increasing field. This is in agreement with the previously reported observations derived from magnetization measurements [39]. In terms of the trend of Φ with temperature, a gradual transition from the inverse to the direct magnetocaloric response is observed near-room temperature (325 K). This agrees with the change of sign as seen in the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} graph in the top panel of Fig. 3 d. Given that the degree of overlap between FOPT and SOPT is smaller in this case, it is possible to examine the transition region in greater detail than in the previously assessed conventional Heusler alloy. It is worth mentioning that the different pattern in the transition from inverse to direct magnetocaloric effect in $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ and $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$, with a characteristic peak in the former and more monotonic in the latter, might be useful for analyzing the dynamics of the phase transition.

To demonstrate that there is an intrinsic difference between the phase lag of second- and first-order phase transitions, Fig. 5 shows the frequency dependence of the amplitude and phase lag for Gd and $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ for a maximum magnetic field of 0.5 T in a narrow temperature range near the phase transition. It is evident that while Gd does not show a peak in Φ for any of the exciting frequencies, $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ clearly shows a frequency-dependent peak in the thermal environment of the transformation. It is worth noting, however, that for very low frequencies, the experimental conditions cannot be considered adiabatic, which affects the magnitude of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} .

It is important to compare the curves of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} obtained using LIT with those of ΔS_{iso} obtained by magnetometry measurements, both for the same maximum applied magnetic field of 1.5 T (Fig. 6). A primary observation is the temperatures of the peak responses for each sample: as the peaks are associated with the occurrence of phase transitions, their temperatures would coincide for both methods of characterization. More significantly, a comparison of the peak magnitudes for the different compositions is necessary. While the SOPT of Gd presents the highest $|\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}|$ among all the studied samples, its performance is relatively modest when assessed by the $|\Delta S_{iso}|$ metric. On the other hand, the FOPT of the all-*d*-metal Heusler alloy demonstrates superior performance in terms of $|\Delta S_{iso}|$ peak response but shows a modest response of $|\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}|$. This suggests that the hysteresis associated with the FOPT is a limiting factor for the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} response. Materials with FOPT suffer substantial degradation in performance when assessing ΔT_{ad}^{rev} instead of ΔS_{iso} as a metric. This is particularly pronounced in $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ and $\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ Heusler alloys, which display magneto-structural transitions coupled with significant thermal hysteresis, in contrast to $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$, which presents a magneto-elastic transition with lower hysteresis. The values of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} obtained for the series of investigated alloys are comparable to those reported in the literature: Ni-Mn-In-based [70–72], Ni-Mn-Sn-based [73,74], Hf-Ta-Fe [75] and La(Fe,Si)₁₃ families [76], for the same moderate magnetic field of 1.5 T.

Despite the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} response is considered reversible with respect to magnetic field oscillations, it is relevant to consider the potential thermal hysteresis that remains in the signal. To address this, both heating

Fig. 3. Evolution of the reversible adiabatic temperature change and the phase shift from the reference oscillating magnetic field, with temperature, in Gd (a), LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H (b), Ni_{48.6}Mn_{35.9}In_{15.5} (c) and Ni₃₆Co₁₄Mn₃₅Ti₁₅ (d).

Fig. 4. Comparison of the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} obtained from conventional (blue squares), average of the conventional (green triangles) and lock-in (orange spheres) IRT for the $Ni_{48.6}Mn_{35.9}In_{15.5}$ sample submitted to a maximum magnetic field of 0.2 T. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Frequency dependence of the evolution of the reversible adiabatic temperature change and the phase shift, with temperature, in Gd and $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$.

and cooling measurements were performed for those materials exhibiting FOPT: $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$, $Ni_{48.6}Mn_{35.9}In_{15.5}$ and $Ni_{36}Co_{14}Mn_{35}Ti_{15}$ (Figs. 7, 8 and 9, respectively). In all instances, a maximum applied magnetic field of 1.5 T was used. Both the $\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}(T)$ curves as well as the local ΔT_{ad}^{rev} maps for selected temperature sampling points are presented in these figures. The temperature-dependent curves reveal a difference between the heating and cooling branches within the temperature range associated with the FOPTs. It is noteworthy that the SOPT occurring at elevated temperatures for $Ni_{48.6}Mn_{35.9}In_{15.5}$ (points *b* and *d* in Fig. 8) exhibits a perfectly reversible response, in agreement with the type of an hysteretic transition. Furthermore, it is significant that the $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$ sample shows considerably less thermal irreversibility than the Heusler alloys. This difference can be attributed to two factors. Firstly, the thermal hysteresis of $\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}(T)$ is limited by the thermal hysteresis of the FOPT (as mentioned above, this corresponds to

Fig. 6. Above, temperature dependence of ΔS_{iso} in Gd (green squares), $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$ (blue triangles), $Ni_{48.6}Mn_{35.9}In_{15.5}$ (black squares) and $Ni_{36}Co_{14}Mn_{35}Ti_{15}$ (red circles) samples (results obtained from magnetometry measurements). Below, ΔT_{ad}^{rev} obtained from the LIT device. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2.2 K for $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$, in contrast to up to 23.4 K for the Heusler alloys). Secondly, $\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}(T)$ will show no thermal hysteresis when the driving field is large enough to saturate the transition. Fig. 7 clearly shows that 1.5 T is adequate to saturate the transition of $LaFe_{11.38}Mn_{0.28}Si_{1.34}-H$, thus removing hysteresis in $\Delta T_{ad}^{rev}(T)$ for this sample. However, it remains far from saturation for the two Heusler alloys. When the field is sufficiently large to saturate the material during each application/removal of the field (which was not achievable for the studied Heusler alloys within our experimental setup), both the heating and cooling responses should be similar, consistent with the magnetocalorimetry experiments presented in ref. [77].

While the reversible contribution to ΔS_{iso} can be estimated from the overlap between the heating and cooling $\Delta S_{iso}(T)$ curves [56], this estimation presumes that the transition is fully completed and, consequently, that the reversible contribution exhibits no thermal hysteresis. The results presented for ΔT_{ad}^{rev} clearly indicate that, particularly in smaller fields, thermal hysteresis remains present. From a practical point of view, the presence of this hysteresis in non-saturating conditions should be taken into account in the design of efficient devices with limited values of applied field.

The spatially resolved images of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} in Figs. 7, 8 and 9, corresponding to the specific temperature sampling points depicted in the graphs, show two notable features. First, a gradient of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} from the center of the samples toward their edges is detected, resulting from the

Fig. 7. (Center graph) The evolution of the heating and cooling branches of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} with temperature in $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ for a maximum applied magnetic field of 1.5 T. (Images a and b) ΔT_{ad}^{rev} of each pixel as a result of the lock-in processing of all images for points a and b highlighted in the graph.

Fig. 8. (Center graph) The evolution of the heating and cooling branches of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} with temperature in $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ for a maximum applied magnetic field of 1.5 T. (Images a, b, c and d) ΔT_{ad}^{rev} of each pixel as a result of lock-in processing of all images for points a, b, c and d highlighted in the graph.

greater influence of the surroundings on the local temperature of the sample near the periphery. This indicates that adiabaticity is not fully achieved. Therefore, all temperature curves presented in this article were obtained from the central region of the samples. Secondly, another gradient is detectable beyond the sample borders toward the sample holder. This is attributed to the thermal conductivity of the sample holder, including the GE varnish used for mounting the sample. This effect is particularly pronounced in the $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ sample as shown in Fig. 7, due to its smaller size and reduced thermal mass.

4. Conclusions

In this work, several magnetocaloric materials exhibiting various types of phase transitions near room temperature were characterized for their reversible adiabatic temperature change: (1) Gd, with a second-order phase transition; (2) a $\text{LaFe}_{11.38}\text{Mn}_{0.28}\text{Si}_{1.34}\text{-H}$ alloy with a first-order magneto-elastic transition; (3) $\text{Ni}_{48.6}\text{Mn}_{35.9}\text{In}_{15.5}$ Heusler alloy with a first-order magneto-structural transition and (4)

$\text{Ni}_{36}\text{Co}_{14}\text{Mn}_{35}\text{Ti}_{15}$ all-*d*-metal Heusler alloy, also with a magneto-structural transition but with reduced overlap between the martensitic and Curie transitions compared to previous alloy.

The lock-in thermography (LIT) technique is identified as an accurate tool for characterizing the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} responses of these materials. The significantly enhanced resolution provided by LIT, in contrast to conventional thermography, enables the reliable detection of features that would be otherwise obscured by noise, such as the emergence of the FOPT in Heusler alloys driven by low fields. Hysteresis presents itself with two negative consequences: on the one hand, thermal hysteresis reduces the ΔT_{ad}^{rev} of FOPT materials, making them less appealing for applications than what ΔS_{iso} might indicate. On the other hand, the application of non-saturating fields causes ΔT_{ad}^{rev} to keep a certain degree of thermal hysteresis that must be considered in device design. Therefore, the MCE response must be characterized under dynamic conditions that closely resemble actual operating conditions in refrigeration devices.

Fig. 9. (Center graph) The evolution of the heating and cooling branches of ΔT_{ad}^{rev} with temperature in $Ni_{36}Co_{14}Mn_{35}Ti_{15}$ for a maximum applied magnetic field of 1.5 T. (Images a, b, c and d) ΔT_{ad}^{rev} of each pixel as a result of lock-in processing of all images for points a, b, c and d highlighted in the graph.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jorge Revuelta-Losada: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Aun N. Khan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Luis M. Moreno-Ramírez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Jia Yan Law:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Anit K. Giri:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Victorino Franco:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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